

ISic2987

I.Sicily inscription 2987

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

accounts

Material

limestone (breccia)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del

Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645339

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1966.0512

Manganaro, G. 1964. Iscrizioni latine e greche dal nuovo edificio termale di Taormina. *Cronache di archeologia e di storia dell'arte*. 3: 38-68. At 42-52 tav.17-18

Manganaro, G. 1988. Le tavole finanziare di Tauromenion. In Knoepfler, D. (eds.), *Comptes et inventaires dans la cité grecque: actes du colloque international*

d'épigraphique tenu à Neuchâtel du 23 au 26 septembre 1986 en l'honneur de J.Tréheux. Neuchâtel. pp. 155-190.

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